

An Analysis of Modern Trends in Teacher Education

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Abstract

This is a descriptive study. Objectives of the research included: examination of modern tendencies in Teacher Education and find out the breaks and give ideas for improvement of Teacher Education Programs of the region. The population of the research was all teacher education organizations of the province. The sample comprised 55 Course instructors of these institutions. The device of the research analysis was a questionnaire. The data was analyzed and the result was shown in percentage in tables. The literature review explored diverse directions of the concern and reflected the requirements of Teacher Education and Transformations, teachers Quality, Teachers Competencies and Policy. The traditional trend is in practice and the pursuit of quality scares teaching. It is recommended in the research report that technology integration in Teacher Education. The research suggests that the government should take timely notice of the need and importance of the use of modern technologies.

Key Words

Modern Trends, Electronic devices, Web-based, Learning, Quality of Teachers

Introduction

Training of teacher and the rapid development of IT technology have brought frequent changes in Education. The use of Computer Assisted Instruction, Online education programs and Distance Education Programs are becoming popular nowadays.

The National Educational Policy (2009:52) stresses the usage of ICT and right to use internet facilities for students and also for teachers, and the suitable excerpts from Government's policies clearly designated the essential and implications of the new technologies and its integration in the teacher education programs of the country. No substantial pains have been made to speed-up the procedure and bring the teacher training program of Pakistan at par with the global situation and necessities of the present age.

Teo, et. al. (2011, p.1357) documented many educational schemes of the world, where the addition of technology has been endured amongst the top urgencies in policy making, curriculum development and financial planning. The government needs to inspire key creativities and make wide structures in educational institutions. Learning processes take placed within and beyond the traditional system through e-learning. Many teachers of educational organizations and those who make policy have taken advantage of the adjustability of online learning process to provide the mandatory inputs to students at all levels of education.

The study discovers:

1. Modern trends in Teacher Education program and the use of ICT.
2. The areas of improvement related to ICT.

Significance of the Study

The study is significance in the sense that firstly it has unveiled modern trends and investigated changes across the globe in Teacher Education program. Secondly it has identified the gaps in existing teacher education program of the province. The study provided some implementable suggestions for the departments of education, institutes of teacher education programs and policy makers for teacher education to prepare a strategic plan for the provincial teacher education program at par with global teacher education program.

Research Questions

1. What are the global modern trends in Teacher Education program?
2. What are the gaps in Teacher Education?
3. How this program could be improved?

Literature Review

For the purpose of investigation of research questions relevant literature to teacher education and modern trends was reviewed. In the following some of its instances have been cited.

Pandey (2012:8) documented training and education of the teachers are vital to shape the learners with more developed competencies to organization with diverse ecological, sociological and politics issues. This progressive aspect needs trained teachers according to the philosophies of education. The recent propensity of alterations in professional growth of teachers' demands measuring and reviewing the attainable standards and good performs throughout the world. The advanced countries of the world like UK and USA are more interested to reexamine various features of their present Professional Development programs of teacher for more improvement.

UNESCO (2012, p.24) the usage of mobile was emphasized and made necessary for effective education. Its use was further improved in different areas of training and professional development activities. In Communicational processes mobile could be used with video calls service and wireless broadband. Teacher may use mobile for assessment of lessons and also to feedback for improving their teaching practices.

Khursheed and Ansari (2012, p.2) said that there is an unmistakable distinction between the way of life and the manner in which they figure out how to lead life inside and out of schools in the evolving scene. It is fundamental to guarantee that teachers have the chances to achieve the advanced advances as the intersection point isn't exactly noticeable in educator preparing programs.

Wang (2002, p.3-4) educated about the significance of innovation for further enhancement of training framework and saw that future educators require to be set up with devices for incorporating innovation into the instructing and learning process. This straightforwardly connects the thought with the frames of mind controlled by the instructors as it is their practices that decide the accomplishment of Teacher Education programs that instill in them the energy in regard to the utilization of present day offices for realizing enhancement in classroom rehearses and their very own convictions. It likewise suggested that such mental and passionate examples are basic to comprehend in light of the fact that this will give headings to instructor mentor to better planning of their work for the preparation of potential educators.

Walsh and Vannatta (2001, p.63) expressed that changes have been seen after some time in the practices of instructors with respect to the utilization of innovation for the improvement of educating and adapting particularly in real classroom circumstances. They further investigated that in the principal year of their exploration, understudies progressed toward becoming specialists to a more noteworthy degree in utilizing the different PC programming and applications at the same time, in the meantime, they felt the desperate need to acquire an ever increasing number of cutting edge apparatuses preparing so as to coordinate data innovation with the educating and learning process. The members of the exploration endeavors confronted the hardship as far as future utilization of innovation in classrooms.

Beyerback, et. al. (2001, p.105-107) recorded an announcement by an examination member that the members learnt hypothesis of PCs yet didn't have even an inkling how to interface hypothesis with training for their application. He further referenced to the view with respect to the student that innovation prepared classroom implies an instructional stay with numerous PCs where they would be given chances to utilize PCs how they would have preferred for accomplishing their ideal objectives. The utilization of innovation was idea as an additional activity. It was additionally recognized that an expanded capability inside the setting of specialized parts of coordinating innovation into training. The past thoughts controlled by the educators have been changed by utilizing the mechanical devices in the classroom as the understudies turned out to be progressively talented as far as utilizing ICT for the improvement of their examination abilities and achievement of different assignments. Also, their consideration proceeded to meet the aims.

Masovic, Saracevic & Kamberovic (2011), electronic-learning is a progressed teaching methodology for online training has drawn the consideration of understudies and educators because of the expanding enthusiasm for this kind of instructive circles the world over. The materials for the courses are sorted out and the learning targets are distinguished to be accomplished. Every one of the substance of the courses accumulated and are made accessible on web for which the utilization of Learning Management System is the fundamental innovation for which programming has turned out to be inescapable.

Laurillard (1993, p.39) demonstrated that it is indispensable to present data and correspondence innovation at the classroom level for enhanced instructing techniques. At present a large portion of the understudies know about

the advanced condition of the world and lion's share of them are as of now utilizing it for correspondence, socialization and communication with one another. It gives chances of expert improvement to all students to take profit by it. The understudies can likewise make virtual visits in various piece of the world. Materials of their enthusiasm on various points can likewise be perused by them. The investigation further demonstrates that Multimedia and Web correspondence upheld forms between the understudies and instructor. These outcomes demonstrated that there were a few instructional connections that helped understudies to increase further understanding when speaking with one another, although the instructor still assumed a key job in the learning procedure.

Clarke (2003, p.17) showed that, in instructive improvements, the use of innovation will absolutely encourage the client to have a simple access to online office previously advanced by instructors all together that they could utilize constrained skills. Any one incorporating an uncommon utilize with visual deficiency can likewise interface him/her to a site for learning through web-based mentoring and other online assets.

Gillett et al (2003, pp. 2-3) shared that internet instructing and learning assets give elective chances to instructive establishments for extra employments. Discoveries of individual meetings with members at present take part in an on line learning program, featured the need of utilizing web-based learning assets with the point for enhancing the scholarly accomplishments of the students and showing abilities of facilitators. The sharing of information among the key performing artists assumes an imperative job in further enhancing the learning condition. Regulating whole projects of study, teaching cross breed courses and use of viable web-based encouraging instructional methods can likewise perform many tasks in this unique situation.

According to Meredith (2004, pp.1-2) virtual libraries are vital in presenting a bridge among teacher training, educational disciplines within the arts and sciences. Effective use of teaching strategies requires information related to a selected discipline and underneath-standing of the pedagogy. It further calls for the use of latest resources and educational gear. Changing and alternations in teaching and getting to know need edition of latest traits and resources advanced in educational disciplines to be used in teacher schooling curricula. Teachers ought to be prepared and skilled well to use those methods and resources efficaciously in lecture room practices. Digital Library additionally presents opportunities of certainly journeying specific websites and pick out required cloth within quick time. Seda (2006, p.24) said that internet is in not in usual usage for approximately one decade that brought major trade change within the idea in lifestyles fashion as the cutting-edge developments for conversation. E-gaining of knowledge, as a clean version of informal getting to know, is implemented through the internet era and involves the instructive sports, which do no longer want the life of the trainer and learner at the equal time and same area. Sessoms (2008, p.89) shared that version for considering new methodologies to teaching is the joint attempt for production of interactive boards and internet 2.0. Tutors are chargeable for lesson planning, use of latest era and powerful teaching strategies. However, students are held accountable for attainment of knowledge and further sharing it with other colleagues. Instructor makes use of version of coaching for developing know-how and explaining standards with assist of arms on and concrete examples in interactive mastering stage. Herrington Mantei and Ferry (2008, p.419) said that I Pads and cell telephones at the moment are typically used among students, but teachers are still not very assured to utilize this generation for teaching getting to know purposes and academically those are used in advanced and applicable way. Teachers try for to grow to be informed of new technology via traditional expert assets along with journals and that records are still very complicated for his or her present stage of expertise. The important supply of tutorial technologies are computers, audio-visual mastering control structures and software program applications gear that may be utilized by instructors when persevering with expert improvement activities are practiced. Herrington et al (2008, p.1) noted that using private mobiles is extra beneficial among the college students in preference to universities facilitators. According to Postle and Tyler (2010, p.61) early on line approaches to coaching and studying have been confined by way of the extent and satisfactory of interplay to be had among trainer and pupil and among pupil and pupil. Early implementation of e-mastering in higher education has no longer led to giant intrusions into the sphere of instructor training. Online methods would possibly provide a capability to control exceptional at scale, percentage assets throughout networks and, importantly, provide more flexibility of revision in time and area. Online processes can offer opportunity academic stories that mission the validity of vicinity-based fashions to represent the great way to deliver fine education inside the associated establishments. Hunter and Daly (2013, p.18) determined that the responses from pre-service instructors of 3 iPads programs changed into discovered beneficial for identification of sight phrases and for spelling.

Ezati (2013, p.35) contemplated that normal modifications in training setting resulting from dynamic economic system, politics, and global tendencies amongst others, number one training must preserve aspect via aspect along with these tendencies. Government designs new curriculum for number one schools, but the trade remains slow in tempo. Teacher trainers aren't acquainted with the brand new tendencies in education together with Information and Communication Technology in coaching and gaining knowledge of, gender, students focused schooling. It is

likewise located that the curriculum of the trainer education schools isn't up to the requirements required requirements.

Skype

Bhaskar (2015) revealed that the role of latest technology is important in the scenario of the 21st century as it helps deciding the rising matters and challenges of teacher training. The teachers use various technical tools and methods for this purpose consisting video conferencing etc. The use of Skype is another significant submission which has a logical system and having silent features like, call number, call Skype to Skype, and call through video as per necessities of the user. It can also be used for SMS service. Similarly, various papers, videos and pictures can also be shared with individual and groups as well. Facilitation and support from subject's experts and professionals can also be availed through Skype. The stated forum can also be used by parents, teachers and educators for holding meeting and discussing essential area and topics for developments different skills of students.

Methodology

The nature of this study was descriptive. The respondents were the instructors of teacher education institutes. For the data collection proper permission was obtained therefore, data was collection in a convenient setting.

Research Tool & Analysis

Questionnaire was developed to collect data from the above-mentioned respondents; collected data was then analyzed on 3 Likert's Scale. Quantitative result was shown in tabular form.

Responses Interpretations

Table 1. Are you Aware of new Trends in Teacher Training?

Respondents	Number	%
disagree	18	32.7
agree	37	67.3
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

The above table shows that majority (67.3) of the instructors are aware of the modern trends of teachers education, while 32.7 % of the instructors were not aware of the moderen trends. "TO SOME EXTENT" option was totally ignored. The frequency was 37 and 18 % accordingly.

Table 2. Do you know the Reflectional Diary?

Responses	No	Percent
NO	34	61.8
YES	21	38.2
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 2 shows that majority of the instructors 61.8% were unaware of reflection diaries while only 38.2 % were aware of it. "TO SOME EXTENT" option was totally ignored. The frequency was 34 and 21 % accordingly.

Table 3. Do you Conduct Educational Seminars in your Institution?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	27	49.1
YES	28	50.9
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 3 shows very close relationship with both of the side of the respondents. Responses in Yes were 50.9 % and "No" responses were 49.1 % which are very close to each other. "TO SOME EXTENT" option was totally ignored. Frequency was 27 and 28 accordingly.

Table 4. Practicum is the most Important part of Teacher Education Do you do it?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	14	25.5
YES	41	74.5
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Most of the instructors do practicum in their institutions which 74.5 % while 25.5% gave their answer in No. “TO SOME EXTENT” option was ignored. Frequency was 14 and 41 accordingly.

Table 1. Do you plan Web based Teaching?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	45	81.8
YES	9	16.4
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	54	98.2

Table 5 shows that majority (81.8%) of the instructors’ teaching was not web based while only 16.4 % said Yes, their teaching planning is web based. “TO SOME EXTENT” option was totally ignored. The Frequency of “Yes” and “No” was 45 and 9 accordingly.

Table 6. Do you Utilize Video Conferencing?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	54	98.2
YES	1	1.8
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Result shows that 98.2% of the instructors were not utilizing video conferencing and only 1.8 % instructors said they use it. “TO SOME EXTENT” option was ignored. Frequency of “No” and “Yes” was 54 and 1 accordingly.

Table 7. Do you have a Digital library in your Institution?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	54	98.2
YES	1	1.8
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 7 shows that 98.2 % instructors don’t use digital library in their institute while 1.8 % instructors said “Yes” they use it. “TO SOME EXTENT” option was ignored. Frequency was 54 and 1 out of 55 accordingly.

Table 8. Do you use E-Portfolio in your Institute?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	49	89.1
YES	6	10.9
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 8 gives the result that only 10.9 % of the instructors use E-Portfolio while 89.1 % instructors do not use it which very significant and high number of respondents. “TO SOME EXTENT” option was totally ignored. Frequency of “No” and “Yes” was 49 and 6 accordingly.

Table 9. Do you use Skype for Teaching and Learning Purposes?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	53	96.4
YES	2	3.6
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

96.4 % of the instructors were not using Skype for the very purpose, while only 3.6 % were using it. "TO SOME EXTENT" option was ignored by them. Frequency was 35 and 2 accordingly.

Table 10. Do you use Mobile Phones for Teaching Purposes?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	43	78.2
YES	12	21.8
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 10 shows that 78.2% of the instructors were not using Mobile Phones for the teaching while 21.8 % of the instructors were using it for the purpose. "TO SOME EXTENT" option was totally ignored by the Instructors.

Table 2. Do you use Tablets for Teaching Purposes?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	48	87.3
YES	7	12.7
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 11 shows that 87.3 % of the instructors were not using Tablets while only 12.7 % of the instructors were using it for the purpose. "TO SOME EXTENT" option was totally ignored. Frequency was 48 and 7 accordingly.

Table 12. Do you use Laptops for Teaching Purposes?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	44	80.0
YES	11	20.0
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 12 shows that 80.0 % of the instructors were not using Laptop while only 20.0 % of the instructors were using it for the purpose. "TO SOME EXTENT" option was totally ignored. Frequency was 44 and 11 accordingly.

Table 13. Do you use Web cameras in your Institute?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	53	96.4
YES	2	3.6
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 13 shows that 96.4 % of the instructors were not using a Web Camera while only 3.6 % of the instructors were using it. "TO SOME EXTENT" was ignored. Frequency was 53 and 2 accordingly.

Table 3. Do you use GPS devices in your Institute?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	54	98.2
YES	1	1.8
TO SOME EXTENT	0	0
Total	55	100.0

Table 14 shows that 98.2 % of the instructors "No" while only 1.8 % of the instructors said "Yes" they use these devices in their institutes. "TO SOME EXTENT" option was totally ignored. Frequency was 54 and 1 accordingly.

Table 4: You know about NPS based on Modern Trends?

Responses	Frequency	Percent
NO	13	23.6
YES	21	38.2

TO SOME EXTENT	21	38.2
Total	55	100.0

Table 15 shows the result that 23.6% of the instructors said “No” while 38.2% of the instructors said “Yes” they know National Professional Standards. 38.2% instructors said, “To Some Extent” Frequency was 13, 21 and 21 accordingly.

Findings

Key findings of the study were the following.

1. The majority of the Instructors were aware of the modern trends in teacher education. The “TO SOME EXTENT” option was completely ignored by the instructors throughout the questions except the last questions.
2. Although the Instructors admitted that they are aware of modern trends in teacher education but even then, 61.8 % of the instructors were unaware of reflection diaries which are used in almost all the advance countries and many quality private institutions also only 38.2 % were aware of it which is very low number.
3. In conduction of Educational seminars responses in Yes were 50.9 % and “No” were 49.1 % which are very close to each other.
4. Majority (74.5 %) of the instructors were doing practicum in their institutions while 25.5% were not doing it.
5. Thus, web based, Video conferencing, digital library, E-Portfolio and Skype, Mobile Phones, Tablets, Laptop, Web Camera and GPS devices, were almost totally ignored and were not used by the instructors.
6. The last thing that about 24 instructors did not know National Professional Standards, 38 % of the instructors knew while the same number of instructors said to some extent.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researcher reached to the conclusion that:

The researcher exposed many modern trends in teacher education. But it was found that: Although many of the instructors who taught in various well known and reputed teacher education institutions were blank about the modern technologies. And these modern technologies have been considered in almost all over the world as modern trends to be used for education purposes especially in teacher education institutions. But unfortunately, our education institutions are still using only traditional methods for teaching which is only lecture method and none of the advanced method or devices mentioned in the study are used. This is our dilemma that we could not bring such change in our education system to put the nation on the track towards its destination.

The following are the key recommendations of the study.

1. All Teacher Education Institutions may be provided enough funds for the purchase of modern electronic devices.
2. A well-managed lab in each teacher education institution may be established where all or most of the electronic device may displayed to the teacher educators and prospective teachers and they may be familiarized with these devices.
3. A well experience trainer may be provided to all the teacher education institutions and faculty may be given proper training to use such devices.
4. Such devices may also be set in the classrooms and instructors may be made bound to teach as per the modern trends and make their learners aware of it.
5. Time to time observational visits may also be conducted to check the utilization of the modern devices and teaching.
6. Instructors of teacher education institutions may also be given some visits of the advance countries to observe and get training in modern trends in education.

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